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Low-Thrust Propulsion and Drift Orbit Optimization for Multi-Client Servicing Missions in Low Earth Orbit

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Abstract

This paper presents a general approach to solve multi-client space logistics path optimization problems in the case of low-thrust propulsion. The methodology accounts for key time-dependent factors, including orbital perturbations (secular J_2 and drag), eclipse propulsion constraints, and servicer fuel mass depletion. A low-thrust transfer strategy, consisting of three phases (thrust-coast-thrust), is employed, utilizing a drift orbit to correct the difference in Right Ascension of the Ascending Node. The drift orbit parameters are optimized by using a Non-Linear Programming algorithm to minimize the fuel cost associated with the transfer while satisfying maximum time of flight constraint. An optimization is conducted for all possible transfers (three-element targeting) between the satellites of a dataset on a two-dimensional discrete grid of initial servicer mass and departure time. This procedure creates two four-variable matrices representing the cost of each possible visitation in terms of fuel consumption and time of flight. The matrices are then interpolated to efficiently solve a general path optimization problem by using a genetic algorithm. Two test cases are analyzed for datasets consisting of 12 and 20 satellites in Low Earth Orbit, respectively. The first addresses an optimal open tour problem where the servicer must visit all satellites once while minimizing total fuel consumption. The second addresses an on-orbit refueling problem where the servicer must refuel as many satellites as possible. The mission scenario is generalized to consider a priority index associated with each client; servicing time and fuel mass constraints are also taken into account.

Keywords: Astrodynamics, Space Logistics, Low-thrust Propulsion, Traveling Salesman Problem.

1. Introduction

Over the past decades, various mission types involving servicer spacecraft visiting multiple orbital locations have been proposed and analyzed. Space Logistics is defined as the theory and practice of driving space system design for operability and supportability, and of managing the flow of materiel, services, and information needed throughout a space system lifecycle ¹.

In-Space Assembly and Manufacturing (ISAM) [1] and on-orbit fuel depot positioning missions [2] are among the application areas of greatest interest

¹AIAA Space Logistics Technical Committee website, <https://www.aiaa-sltc.org/>

to space logistics. These missions involve multiple rendezvous maneuvers between the servicing satellite and each client satellite. Another research area of great interest concerns orbital debris mitigation. Different solutions have been proposed to reduce the amount of debris in Low Earth Orbit (LEO); many of them involve the use of an active spacecraft performing a close approach to a set of debris. Finally, some data collecting missions can be mathematically modeled as a multiple visitation problem, where the probe satellite must visit specific points in space to conduct observations. Due to the limited resources available on board the servicer satellite, path optimization tools are essential to efficiently address these problems and meet operational constraints.

Path optimization problems involving multiple rendezvous with moving targets are referred to as *Moving-Target (or time-dependent) Traveling Salesman Problems* (MTTSP). These problems are Non-deterministic Polynomial-time complete [3]; their combinatorial complexities mainly lie in the mixed integer/continuous nature of the variables involved and the proper definition of a distance metric quantifying the cost (propellant, time, or a combination of the two [4]) associated with each individual visiting maneuver (leg). By adopting the term *client* to refer to the orbital states that the servicer must visit, a path optimization problem can be re-conducted to a non-linear time-dependent problem composed of two subproblems [5]:

- I. A functional subproblem, where the cost of each maneuver (*distance metric* or *leg cost function*) is computed by solving an optimal control problem.
- II. A combinatorial subproblem involving the generation of the sequence of clients to visit.

Even considered separately, these two sub-problems are difficult to solve.

Concerning the functional problem, analytical solutions exist only in very simple cases and are mainly distinguished on the basis of the type of propulsion, the orbital perturbations included in the model, the inclusion of the mass depletion and the objective function [6]. The functional optimization problem is usually easier to solve when the servicer is endowed with high-thrust propulsion because of the smaller number of variables [4], [7]–[9]. However, the use of high-thrust propulsion for multiple rendezvous requires a huge amount of fuel limiting its application to a small number of clients. To mitigate this issue, in [9], a passive correction is considered of the Right Ascension of the Ascending Node (RAAN) by exploiting a drift orbit to reduce fuel consumption. An optimal sequence for a four-client open tour is found.

The use of low-thrust propulsion has been proposed as an alternative strategy to service a greater number of satellites [10]–[18]. Due to the complexity of the problem, previously mentioned works adopt assumptions regarding the functional problem and/or the combinatorial one to obtain a solution. A multiple-visitation optimal tour problem for a very

large dataset of asteroids is solved in [10]. However, the distance metric adopted assumes small differences between the orbital elements of the satellites. Furthermore, the servicer fuel mass depletion is neglected. A similar distance metric is used in [11] with the inclusion of the secular J_2 perturbation into the model. The effect of the fuel mass depletion is taken into account by introducing empirical formulas. The optimal tour solution of an active debris removal mission is found. These works both neglect the effects of drag and propulsion constraints due to eclipse phases. In [12], the combinatorial problem is solved by using a distance metric which neglects time-dependent factors; then, the optimal sequence trajectories are obtained by a six-element-targeting feedback controller. A three-phase distance metric including the effects of drag, eclipse propulsion constraint, fuel mass depletion and duty cycle to obtain the cost and the associated trajectories of a five debris removal mission is considered in [13]. A similar problem is addressed in [14] where the functional problem is solved by adopting an algorithm based on Non-Linear-Programming (NLP). The six-element-targeting trajectory is found for a five-piece active debris removal mission. A single-parameter drift orbit is also included to minimize the cost due to RAAN correction. However, in these works the combinatorial problem is not addressed (e.g., the sequence is not optimized). A solution of an optimal tour problem for an active debris removal mission is presented in [16]. The distance metric is derived by assuming an in-plane control acceleration in order to reduce the number of optimization parameters. Averaged dynamics equations and fixed-parameter drift orbits are adopted to solve the functional problem. However, they do not consider propulsion constraints due to eclipse phases.

In [19], the authors of this paper introduced a general approach to solving multi-client space logistics problems by employing a feedback controller to address the functional problem. The combinatorial complexity was mitigated through a data interpolation method. Although the approach accounted for the primary orbital perturbations, it did not leverage the secular J_2 perturbation to optimize fuel-efficient trajectories, a consideration particularly relevant for LEO missions.

In this paper, we propose a general approach that can be applied to different mission scenarios dealing with multiple visitation problems in the low-thrust propulsion context.

In order to solve the functional problem, we adopt a three-phase maneuver distance metric similar to that employed in [13] which takes into consideration the effects of fuel mass depletion, drag, eclipse, and secular J_2 . A fast NLP derivation of the single leg problem is used to find a two-parameter drift orbit that satisfies the operational constraints while minimizing the cost associated with active RAAN correction. All possible visitation costs are then computed for a discrete number of servicer mass and departure time. Bi-linear interpolation is applied to obtain a quick-to-evaluate continuous approximation of the distance metric. A genetic algorithm is finally run multiple times to ensure convergence to the global optimal sequence. Two application cases exemplify the proposed methodology.

The key contributions of the proposed approach lie in its ability to solve the functional problem by optimizing two-parameter drift orbits, effectively minimizing costs and enhancing mission profitability in LEO. This is achieved while accounting for time-dependent factors, sequencing, and trajectory optimization within a general multi-client path framework.

2. Path Optimization Problem Formulation

The MTTSP represents the archetype of multiple-visitation problems, where a salesman must visit all cities of a dataset once and only once. The cost of each visitation is quantified by a time-dependent function, and the optimal sequence is the one minimizing the sum of the costs.

Path Optimization (PO) Problems represent a more general class of problems where generic constraints and objective function formulation are taken into consideration [5]. The global optimization problem can be mathematically defined by mixing integer variables, real variables, and functions.

Let N_{sat} be the number of satellites considered. Let $\mathcal{D} = \{d_1, \dots, d_i, \dots, d_{N_d}\}$, where $d_i \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$, be a set of positive integers whose elements are the IDs of the $N_d \leq N_{sat}$ satellites

to be visited. Let $\mathbf{ToF} = [t_1, \dots, t_i, \dots, t_{N_d}]$, where $t_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, be a vector of real numbers containing the time of each rendezvous, and let $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathbf{T}_1(t), \dots, \mathbf{T}_i(t), \dots, \mathbf{T}_{N_d-1}(t)\}$ be a set of functions where $\mathbf{T}_i(t)$ represents the control law to perform the i^{th} visitation (e.g., $\mathbf{T}_i(t)$ is the quantity associated with the solution of the functional problem). Denoting with $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, N_d\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, N_d - 1\}$, the PO-Problem can be stated as follows [19]

Problem 1. Path Optimization Problem

$$\min_{\mathcal{D}, \mathbf{ToF}, \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d-1} C_i(d_i, d_{i+1}, t_i, t_{i+1}, \mathbf{T}_i(t), \mathbf{p})$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_S(t) &= \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}_S(t), \mathbf{T}_i(t)) && \forall t, \forall i \in \mathcal{M} \\ \|\mathbf{T}_i(t)\| &\leq T_{max} && \forall t, \forall i \in \mathcal{M} \\ \dot{\mathbf{X}}_i(t) &= \mathbf{G}_i(\mathbf{X}_i(t), \mathbf{T}_i^c(t)) && \forall t, \forall i \in \mathcal{K} \\ \mathbf{X}_S(t_0) &= \mathbf{X}_{S,0} \\ \mathbf{X}_i(t_0) &= \mathbf{X}_{i,0} && \forall i \in \mathcal{K} \\ \mathbf{X}_{S,[1:6]}(t_i) &= \mathbf{X}_{d_i,[1:6]}(t_i) && \forall i \in \mathcal{K} \\ \mathbf{Z}_{eq}(\mathcal{D}, \mathbf{X}_S, \mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{N_d}, \mathbf{ToF}, \mathcal{T}) &= 0 \\ \mathbf{Z}_{ineq}(\mathcal{D}, \mathbf{X}_S, \mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{N_d}, \mathbf{ToF}, \mathcal{T}) &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

where T_{max} is the maximum available thrust of the servicer. $C_i(d_i, d_{i+1}, t_i, t_{i+1}, T_i(t), \mathbf{p})$ denotes the cost of going from satellite d_i at time t_i to satellite d_{i+1} at time t_{i+1} using the control law $\mathbf{T}_i(t)$, and \mathbf{p} is a vector of parameters (e.g., propulsion system specific impulse, servicer coefficient of drag, etc.). $\mathbf{X}_S(t) = [a(t), e(t), i(t), \Omega(t), \omega(t), \theta(t), m(t)]_S^T$ is the state of the servicer, where $a(t)$ is the semi-major axis, $e(t)$ the eccentricity, $i(t)$ the inclination, $\omega(t)$ the argument of perigee, $\Omega(t)$ the Right Ascension of the Ascending Node, $\theta(t)$ the true anomaly, and $m(t)$ is the mass; while $\mathbf{X}_i(t)$ represents the state of the i^{th} client. \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{G}_i represent the dynamics of the servicer and the dynamics of i^{th} client, respectively. They are functions of the state and the control thrust acting on the satellite ($\mathbf{T}(t)$ or $\mathbf{T}_i^c(t)$). $\mathbf{X}_{S,0}$ and $\mathbf{X}_{i,0}$ denote the initial boundary conditions, while $\mathbf{X}_{S,[1:6]}(t_i) = \mathbf{X}_{d_i,[1:6]}(t_i)$ represents the rendezvous condition between the servicer and the client, with the subscript $[1 : 6]$ indicating that only the first

six components must be the same at time t_i . Finally, \mathbf{Z}_{eq} and \mathbf{Z}_{ineq} represent other non-linear equality or inequality constraints involving the optimization variables, the state of the satellites and the control laws.

The PO-Problem is defined by the choice of a distance metric and an algorithm to solve for the integer variables, real variables and functions mixed problem. In the following, the dependence of the distance metric on the parameters \mathbf{p} will be assumed and not be explicitly underlined.

3. Functional Subproblem

A distance metric $C(d_i, d_j, t_i, t_j, \mathbf{T}_{i \rightarrow j}(t))$, which quantifies the cost of transferring from satellite orbit d_i to d_j , with departure at time t_i and arrival at time t_j ($t_j \geq t_i$), can be defined a priori for each possible transfer. The functional problem then reduces to finding the control law $\mathbf{T}_{i \rightarrow j}(t)$ by using results from optimal control theory [20]. Some approximations are necessary to reduce the computational burden. The following assumptions are here adopted:

- A.1 Servicer trajectory and client orbits are nearly circular ($e \leq 0.05$).
- A.2 Rendezvous maneuver cost is neglected. The cost difference between a transfer maneuver and a rendezvous maneuver is generally negligible with low-thrust propulsion [21].

By considering the servicer equipped with a low-thrust propulsion system and the two assumptions above, a three-phase maneuver is adopted, consisting of:

1. Transfer from initial state to a drift orbit.
2. Drift orbit.
3. Transfer from the final state of the drift orbit to the final orbit.

The cost of the transfer is represented by the total velocity increment $\Delta V = \Delta V_1 + \Delta V_2 + \Delta V_3$ (where the subscripts indicate the phase they refer to) applied by the servicer's propulsion system to transfer the spacecraft from the initial orbit to the target orbit.

Figure 1 shows a schematic example of a three-phase maneuver in case of near-circular orbits. In

Figure 1: Three-phase maneuver schematic example

the first phase, the servicer is transferred to a drift orbit defined by its semi-major axis a_D and inclination i_D . During the second phase, the RAAN difference is corrected by using differential precession, while propulsion is employed solely to counteract the drag effect. In the final phase, the satellite is transferred to the target orbit. Drag, propulsion constraints due to eclipse phases, and fuel mass depletion effects will be considered during the three phases.

3.1 Three-phase Maneuver Transfer

The computations for the ΔV in Phases 1 and 3 are based on the results presented in [22] and derived using the averaged dynamics equations (see Appendix). During these phases, the servicer is transferred from the initial state (a_i, i_i, Ω_i) to the final state (a_f, i_f, Ω_f) , where the semi-major axis and inclinations (a and i) are actively corrected through an in-plane maneuver while the RAAN (Ω) varies according to the following equation [23]

$$\dot{\Omega}(t) = -\frac{3}{2} J_2 \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a(t)^3}} \left(\frac{R_e}{a(t)} \right)^2 \cos i(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\mu = 3.986 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}^2$ is the gravitational constant, $J_2 = 1.083 \times 10^{-3}$ is the first zonal harmonic coefficient, and $R_e = 6378.137 \text{ km}$ is the Earth's equatorial radius. Given $a(t)$, $i(t)$, and Ω_i, Ω_f is obtained by integrating Eq. 1 from t_i to t_f

$$\Omega_f = \Omega_i - \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{3}{2} J_2 \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a(t)^3}} \left(\frac{R_e}{a(t)} \right)^2 \cos i(t) dt \quad (2)$$

In [24], Edelbaum's work [22] is extended to incorporate the effects of secular J_2 , eclipse, and fuel mass depletion through a numerical procedure. With minor adaptations, the same algorithm can also consider the effects of drag [13]. The algorithm for computing the ΔV in these phases is outlined in Algorithm 1, and it incorporates a slight revision compared to the version presented in [13]. In the revised version, the computation of the drag effect (Step 17) has been updated. Specifically, the drag effect is now evaluated at the midpoint between two time steps, t_k and t_{k+1} , rather than solely at t_k as in [13].

Algorithm 1 requires the spacecraft's initial mass m_i , the specific impulse I_{sp} of the propulsion system, the maximum thrust T_{max} , the atmospheric density ρ_0 at reference height H_0 , the coefficient of drag of the servicer CD , its reference aerodynamic surface S , and the number of discretization points N . The function $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$ indicates the signum function, while $w_{ecl}(t, a, i, \Omega)$ is the function computing the eclipse mean time per orbit. The gravity at Earth's surface is $g_0 = 9.80665 \text{ m/s}^2$. The outputs are the total ΔV_f , the updated time of flight Δt , and the total RAAN variation $\Delta\Omega$ in the presence of perturbations. Note that the transfer strategy reported in Algorithm 1 allows a two-orbital-elements targeting (a and i). RAAN correction is performed during the intermediate phase, where differential precession due to secular J_2 is exploited (Eq. 1).

In this work, a circular two-parameter drift orbit is considered, defined by its semi-major axis a_D (or the associated circular velocity V_D) and inclination (i_D). The total servicer RAAN variation is the sum of the three phases (i.e., $\Delta\Omega_{tot} = \Delta\Omega_1 + \Delta\Omega_2 + \Delta\Omega_3$). The phasing time Δt_2 is computed to match the final client RAAN. The sum of these three sequences allows for a three-orbital-element targeting transfer $(a_i, i_i, \Omega_i) \rightarrow (a_f, i_f, \Omega_f)$, where the total time of flight $T_{oF} = \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2 + \Delta t_3$ depends on the parameters reported in Algorithm 1 and on the drift orbit parameters (a_D and i_D). Algorithm 2 delineates the three-phase maneuver computational steps to reach the final orbit. In Algorithm 2, $\text{mod}(\cdot, 2\pi)$

is the modulus function, while $\Omega_{c,i}$ represents the RAAN of the client at time t_i .

Finally, Algorithm 2 provides two quantities (ΔV and T_{oF}). Once the characteristics of the propulsion system and the inertial properties of the servicer have been chosen, the ΔV and T_{oF} required for a three-phase maneuver transfer can be expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &= \Delta V(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_D, i_D) \\ T_{oF} &= T_{oF}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_D, i_D) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where t_i represents the initial time of the transfer, m_i the servicer initial mass, while a_D and i_D are the drift orbit parameters.

The initial and target orbit states have been reduced to two integer variables, d_j and d_k , respectively. Given a dataset of N_{sat} satellites defined by their initial Keplerian elements at the start time t_0 , it is possible to uniquely associate an integer l with each of them, ranging from 1 to N_{sat} . If the dynamics $\dot{\mathbf{X}}_l(t) \forall t$ are known, the complete state at time t_i can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{X}_l(t_i) = \int_{t_0}^{t_i} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_l(t) dt \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_l(t_0)$ is the state of the l^{th} satellite at the start time.

In conclusion, from t_i , d_j and d_k and Eq. 4, it is possible to obtain a_i , i_i , Ω_i , a_f , i_f and $\Omega_{c,i}$ needed by Algorithm 2 to compute the transfer cost to visit the satellite identified by d_k starting from the satellite identified by d_j departing at time t_i .

Eqs. 3 are introduced in order to write a distance metric with a similar formalism to that reported in Problem 1 and will be extensively used in the following sections.

3.2 Drift Orbit Parameter Optimization

The drift orbit parameters a_D and i_D are two additional variables in the functional problem. In this work, these parameters have been optimized in order to minimize the ΔV of the transfer. A constraint on the maximum time of flight $T_{oF_{max}}$ must be included to ensure a well-posed problem [13]. Other constraints may include maximum and minimum values for the drift orbit parameters, denoted

Algorithm 1 Minimum-time two-orbital-element targeting $(a_i, i_i) \rightarrow (a_f, i_f)$

Given: $t_i, a_i, a_f, i_i, i_f, \Omega_i, m_i, I_{sp}, T_{max}, \rho_0, H_0, CD, S, N$

1: $V_i = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_i}}, V_f = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_f}}, \Delta i = i_f - i_i, f_t = \frac{T_{max}}{m_i}$

2: $\Delta V_f = \sqrt{V_i^2 + V_f^2 - 2V_i V_f \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \Delta i\right)}$

3: $\beta_0 = \arctan\left(\frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \Delta i\right)}{\frac{V_i}{V_f} - \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \Delta i\right)}\right)$

4: $t_f = \frac{\Delta V_f}{T_{max}} + t_i, \Delta t = \frac{t_f - t_i}{N}$

5: **for** $k = 1$ to N **do**

6: $t_k = t_i + (k - 1)\Delta t$

7: $\Delta V_k = (t_k - t_i)f_t$

8: $a_k = \frac{\mu}{V_i^2 + f_t^2 t_k^2 - 2V_i f_t t_k \cos(\beta_0)}$

9: $v_k = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_k}}$

10: $i_k = i_i + \frac{2 \operatorname{sgn}(\Delta i)}{\pi} \left(\arctan\left(\frac{\Delta V_k - V_i \cos \beta_0}{V_i \sin \beta_0}\right) + \frac{\pi}{2} - \beta_0 \right)$

11: **end for**

12: $\Omega_1 = \Omega_i, m_1 = m_i$

13: **for** $j = 1$ to $N - 1$ **do**

14: $w_{ecl} = w_{ecl}(t_j, a_j, i_j, \Omega_j)$ from [25]

15: $m_{j+1} = m_j \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta V_j}{I_{sp} g_0}}\right)$

16: $\bar{m} = \frac{m_j + m_{j+1}}{2}$

17: $\bar{f}_d = \frac{S \rho_0 CD}{2} \left(\frac{v_j^2}{m_j} e^{-\frac{a_j - R_e}{H_0}} + \frac{v_{j+1}^2}{m_{j+1}} e^{-\frac{a_{j+1} - R_e}{H_0}} \right)$

18: $f_{t,j} = \frac{T_{max}}{\bar{m}} - \bar{f}_d$

19: $t_{j+1} = t_j + \frac{\Delta V_{j+1} - \Delta V_j}{f_{t,j} w_{ecl}}$

20: $\dot{\Omega}_j = -\frac{3}{2} J_2 \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_j^3}} \left(\frac{R_e}{a_j}\right)^2 \cos i_j$

21: $\Omega_{j+1} = \Omega_j + \dot{\Omega}_j(t_{j+1} - t_j)$

22: **end for**

Return: $\Delta V_f, \Delta t = t_N - t_i, \Delta \Omega = \Omega_N - \Omega_i$

Algorithm 2 Three-phase maneuver $(a_i, i_i, \Omega_i) \rightarrow (a_f, i_f, \Omega_f)$

Given: $t_i, a_i, a_f, i_i, i_f, \Omega_i, m_i, I_{sp}, T_{max}, \rho_0, H_0, CD, S, N, \Omega_{c,i}, a_D, i_D$

1: Compute $\Delta V_1, \Delta t_1$ and $\Delta \Omega_1$ from Algorithm 1 to transfer the servicer from initial orbit to the drift orbit $(a_i, i_i) \rightarrow (a_D, i_D)$

2: Compute $\Delta V_3, \Delta t_3$ and $\Delta \Omega_3$ from Algorithm 1 to transfer the servicer from the drift orbit to the final orbit $(a_D, i_D) \rightarrow (a_f, i_f)$

3: Compute the total RAAN variation of the servicer and the client during phases 1 and 3

$$\Delta \Omega_S = \Omega_i + \Delta \Omega_1 + \Delta \Omega_3$$

$$\Delta \Omega_c = \Omega_{c,i} + \dot{\Omega}_c(\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_3)$$

4: Compute Δt_2 needed to match the RAAN difference

$$\Delta t_2 = \frac{\operatorname{mod}(\Delta \Omega_c - \Delta \Omega_S, 2\pi)}{\dot{\Omega}_D - \dot{\Omega}_c}$$

if $\Delta t_2 < 0$

$$\Delta t_2 = -\frac{\operatorname{mod}(2\pi - \Delta \Omega_c - \Delta \Omega_S, 2\pi)}{\dot{\Omega}_D - \dot{\Omega}_c}$$

where $\dot{\Omega}_D$ and $\dot{\Omega}_c$ are computed from Eq. 1

$$\dot{\Omega}_D = -\frac{3}{2} J_2 \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_D^3}} \left(\frac{R_e}{a_D}\right)^2 \cos i_D$$

$$\dot{\Omega}_c = -\frac{3}{2} J_2 \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_f^3}} \left(\frac{R_e}{a_f}\right)^2 \cos i_f$$

5: Compute servicer mass at the beginning of phase 2

$$m_D = m_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta V_1}{I_{sp} g_0}}\right)$$

6: Compute drag acceleration during the phase 2

$$f_{d,2} = \frac{S \rho_0 CD}{2} \frac{\mu}{a_D m_D} e^{-\frac{a_D - R_e}{H_0}}$$

7: Compute ΔV_2 to counteract the drag

$$\Delta V_2 = -\int_0^{\Delta t_2} f_{d,2} dt$$

Return: $\Delta V = \Delta V_1 + \Delta V_2 + \Delta V_3, T_oF = \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2 + \Delta t_3$

as $(a_{D,max}, i_{D,max})$ and $(a_{D,min}, i_{D,min})$, respectively. These constraints arise from various considerations such as drag effects.

Given an initial time t_i , initial mass m_i , and initial and target orbits d_j and d_k , respectively, the problem of minimizing ΔV reduces to a constrained non-linear optimization problem as outlined in Problem 2.

Problem 2. Drift Orbit Parameters Optimization

$$\min_{a_D, i_D} \Delta V(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_D, i_D)$$

subject to

$$a_{D,min} \leq a_D \leq a_{D,max}$$

$$i_{D,min} \leq i_D \leq i_{D,max}$$

$$ToF(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_D, i_D) \leq ToF_{max}$$

The solution to the above problem provides the optimal drift orbit parameters $(a_{D,opt}, i_{D,opt})$, the minimum ΔV , and the associated time of flight

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V_{opt} &= \Delta V_{opt}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k) \\ &= \Delta V(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_{D,opt}, i_{D,opt}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ToF_{opt} &= ToF_{opt}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k) \\ &= ToF(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k, a_{D,opt}, i_{D,opt}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Eqs. 5 and 6 represent the solution of the functional problem considering the assumptions detailed in Sec. 3.1, including effects of fuel mass depletion, eclipse constraints, drag, and a three-phase maneuver with optimal drift orbit parameters.

A distance metric in the form described in Sec. 2 (i.e., $C(d_i, d_j, t_i, t_j, \mathbf{T}_{i \rightarrow j}(t))$) can be constructed from Eqs.5 and 6.

4. General Approach: Time-Varying Matrix Interpolation

The *Time-Varying Matrix Interpolation* method is proposed to efficiently manage the time-variant nature of Problem 1 while maintaining reasonable computational time [19].

The proposed approach involves two main steps:

1. Cost Matrix Computation.

2. Bilinear Interpolation.

The result of this procedure is an approximate but quick-to-evaluate distance metric. Consequently, Problem 1 is reduced to a purely combinatorial problem that can be tackled effectively by various algorithms, one of which is discussed in Sec. 5.

4.1 Cost Matrix Computation

In previous sections, two 4-variable functions were derived (Eqs.5 and 6). For a dataset of N_{sat} satellites, the integer variables d_i are restricted to values in the set $\{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$. In a real mission scenario, the initial mass M_0 , the dry mass of the servicer M_{dry} , the start time $T_{M,0}$, and the total mission duration ΔT_M are either known or design parameters.

Defining the continuous closed intervals $M_C = [M_{dry}, M_0]$ and $T_C = [T_{M,0}, T_{M,0} + \Delta T_M]$, the number of mass points N_M , and the number of time points N_T , the sets $\mathcal{N}_M = \{1, \dots, N_M + 1\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_T = \{1, \dots, N_T + 1\}$, M_C and T_C can be discretized as follows

$$\begin{aligned} M_D &= \{M_1, \dots, M_i, \dots, M_{N_M+1}\} \\ T_D &= \{T_1, \dots, T_l, \dots, T_{N_T+1}\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} M_i &= M_{dry} + (i - 1) \frac{M_0 - M_{dry}}{N_M}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}_M \\ T_l &= T_{M,0} + (l - 1) \frac{\Delta T_M}{N_T}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{N}_T \end{aligned}$$

Eq. 7 represents a discretization of the intervals M_C and T_C into $N_M + 1$ and $N_T + 1$ points, respectively. Using Eqs.5, 6, and 7, two 4-dimensional matrices ($\Delta V_{opt,iljk}$ and $ToF_{opt,iljk}$) can be computed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V_{opt,iljk} &= \Delta V_{opt}(M_i, T_l, d_j, d_k), \\ &\forall i \in \mathcal{N}_M, \forall l \in \mathcal{N}_T, \forall j, k \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ToF_{opt,iljk} &= ToF_{opt}(M_i, T_l, d_j, d_k), \\ &\forall i \in \mathcal{N}_M, \forall l \in \mathcal{N}_T, \forall j, k \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Due to the time-dependent nature of the problem, swapping d_j and d_k in Eqs. 5 and 6 does not yield the same results (i.e., $\Delta V_{opt}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k) \neq \Delta V_{opt}(t_i, m_i, d_k, d_j)$). When $j = k$, the initial state is the same as the final state, leading to $\Delta V =$

Figure 2: $\Delta V_{opt,iljk}$ cost matrix decomposition

$ToF = 0$. Thus, computing Eqs. 8 and 9 necessitates $(N_M + 1)(N_T + 1)(N_{sat} - 1)N_{sat}$ optimizations. The computational burden can become prohibitive if fine initial mass and/or time grids and large datasets are considered. In such cases, parallel computing can be leveraged to calculate $\Delta V_{opt,iljk}$ and $ToF_{opt,iljk}$ within a practical time frame.

Eqs. 8 and 9 provide the costs in terms of fuel and time of flight, respectively, obtained by solving the functional problem for all possible transfers between satellites in a given dataset, for a finite number of servicer initial masses and times.

Figure 2 shows a conceptual visualization of the $\Delta V_{opt,iljk}$ cost matrix in case of $N_{sat} = 3$, $N_M = 3$, and a generic N_T . Colors represent different values of ΔV . The same schematic decomposition applies to $ToF_{opt,iljk}$.

4.2 Bilinear Interpolation

In a real mission scenario, both the initial mass of the servicer and the departure time can take values within specified continuous intervals. Based on the pre-computed matrices, we define two mapping functions, $f_{\Delta V,jk} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $f_{ToF,jk} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which operate on the sub-matrices $\Delta V_{opt,jk} := \Delta V_{opt,iljk}, \forall i, l$ and $ToF_{opt,jk} := ToF_{opt,iljk}, \forall i, l$, as described in Eqs. 10 and 11. These functions approximate the costs over the continuous closed intervals $\forall m_i \in M_C$ and $\forall t_i \in T_C$ introduced in Sec. 4.1.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V_{C,jk} &= \Delta V_{C,jk}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k) \\ &= f_{\Delta V,jk}(t_i, m_i, \Delta V_{opt,jk}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Figure 3: $\Delta V_{C,jk}$ bilinear interpolation example

Figure 4: $ToF_{C,jk}$ bilinear interpolation example

$$\begin{aligned} ToF_{C,jk} &= ToF_{C,jk}(t_i, m_i, d_j, d_k) \\ &= f_{ToF,jk}(t_i, m_i, ToF_{opt,jk}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Eqs. 10 and 11 describe the costs associated with transfers between the d_j and d_k satellites of the dataset. The complete set of mapping functions is defined for all possible transfers as $f_{\Delta V,jk}, \forall j, k \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$ and $f_{ToF,jk}, \forall j, k \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$.

In this work, $f_{\Delta V,jk}$ and $f_{ToF,jk}$ are implemented as bilinear interpolating functions. Figures 3 and 4 show an example of bilinear interpolations for a sample transfer between two Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. The mapping functions $f_{\Delta V,jk}$ and $f_{ToF,jk}$ were applied to pre-computed matrices obtained by discretizing $T_C = [0, 1050]$ days and $M_C = [350, 700]$ kg into 15 and 8 points, respectively ($N_T = 14$ and $N_M = 7$). Each element was calculated by solving the optimal three-phase maneuver problem (Problem 2) with $ToF_{max} = 150$ days.

From Fig. 3, two main insights can be derived. First, the required ΔV is always greater than 1 km/s, indicating a significant difference in Keplerian elements between the satellites. Second, the required ΔV increases with both increasing initial mass and

departure time. This is consistent with the fact that, for a fixed maximum thrust ($T_{max} = 0.236$ N in this example), the available acceleration is higher for lower masses. Additionally, the increase in ΔV with departure time suggests that satellites are drifting apart due to differential node precession, making it more advantageous to visit the target satellite earlier in the mission when $\Delta\Omega$ is smaller. Figure 4 provides insights into the feasibility of the transfer. For most values of initial mass and departure time, it is possible to reach the target within 150 days. However, when $\Delta\Omega$ is high and the available thrust is low, a drift orbit that satisfies the constraints $a_{D,min}, a_{D,max}, \dot{i}_{D,min}, \dot{i}_{D,max}$ does not exist.

As we consider the effects of discretization on the interpolation process, it is clear that a finer discretization would increase both the accuracy of the bilinear interpolation and the computational time required to create the $\Delta V_{opt,iljk}$ and $ToF_{opt,iljk}$, making the choice of N_M and N_T a trade-off between these two factors.

5. Combinatorial Subproblem

The Time-Varying Matrix Interpolation method provides two models, $\Delta V_{C,jk}$ and $ToF_{C,jk}$, representing an approximate solution to the functional problem. These models incorporate both dynamics and control law, thereby reducing Problem 1 to a combinatorial path problem, which can be stated as follows

Problem 3. Combinatorial Path Problem

$$\min_{\mathcal{D}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d-1} D_j (\Delta V_{C,j(j+1)}, ToF_{C,j(j+1)})$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{Z}_{eq}(\mathcal{D}, t_{i,1}, \dots, t_{i,N_d}, m_{i,1}, \dots, m_{i,N_d}) = 0$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{ineq}(\mathcal{D}, t_{i,1}, \dots, t_{i,N_d}, m_{i,1}, \dots, m_{i,N_d}) \leq 0$$

where D_j denotes a generic cost function associated with the transfer from d_j to d_{j+1} , while \mathbf{Z}_{eq} and \mathbf{Z}_{ineq} represent generic equality and inequality constraints, respectively. Though not explicitly stated, both $\Delta V_{C,j(j+1)}$ and $ToF_{C,j(j+1)}$ are considered as functions of $(t_{i,j}, m_{i,j}, d_j, d_{j+1})$.

This problem formulation is applicable to a broad range of real mission scenarios, with its validity being limited only by the assumptions used in deriving the models ($\Delta V_{C,jk}$ and $ToF_{C,jk}$).

Table 1: Satellites' Initial Keplerian Elements

ID	a(km)	i(deg)	Ω (deg)
Satellite - 1	7164.04	86.43	164.8
Satellite - 2	6989.20	86.44	151.3
Satellite - 3	7148.54	86.44	163.1
Satellite - 4	7159.28	86.41	157.9
Satellite - 5	7163.26	86.45	173.5
Satellite - 6	7123.77	86.42	154.0
Satellite - 7	7105.55	86.09	77.07
Satellite - 8	7142.54	86.39	147.4
Satellite - 9	7312.32	86.00	127.3
Satellite - 10	7048.23	86.23	62.44
Satellite - 11	7078.63	86.37	196.4
Satellite - 12	6945.29	86.14	7.535

In order to solve this combinatorial problem, both deterministic and heuristic algorithms can be utilized. In this work, a genetic algorithm with mutation has been implemented to generate sequences satisfying the constraints specified in Problem 3. The genetic algorithm is configured with user-defined parameters: the population size N_{pop} , the maximum number of generations N_{gen} , and the maximum number of stall generations N_{stall} . After each generation, the sequence associated with the minimum cost is selected and saved in case of an improvement in the objective function. The genetic algorithm terminates either when the maximum number of generations N_{gen} is reached or if the objective function does not improve for N_{stall} generation. The efficiency in evaluating the models $\Delta V_{C,jk}$ and $ToF_{C,jk}$ allows for running the algorithm multiple times to ensure convergence towards the global optimum, thus enhancing the reliability of the results.

6. Simulation Results

The proposed methodology has been applied to two multiple-visitation application cases on a set of $N_{sat} = 12$ and $N_{sat} = 20$ orbital elements, respectively, taken from IRIDIUM [12]. The initial orbital elements for the twelve-satellite case are reported in Table 1, while servicer aerodynamic and low-thrust propulsion system specifications (NEXT ion thruster [26]) are reported in Table 2. The three-phase maneuver with optimal drift orbit, described in Sec. 3.1, was used to solve the functional problem. Cost ma-

Table 2: Aerodynamic and Low-thrust Propulsion Servicer Properties

Parameter	Unit	Value
CD	-	2
S	m ²	1.5
I_{sp}	s	4170
T_{max}	N	0.236

Table 3: NLP Algorithm Data

Parameter	Unit	Value
ρ_0	kg/m ³	2.34×10^{-13}
H_0	km	687.00
$a_{D,min}$	km	6728.14
$a_{D,max}$	km	7378.14
$i_{D,min}$	deg	0
$i_{D,max}$	deg	360
ToF_{max}	days	150
N	-	100

trices, computed using Eqs. 5 and 6, were generated for all possible transfers over two discrete intervals of initial servicer masses and departure times. Each satellite's state at time t_i was determined by propagating Eq. 4, considering the secular J_2 effect and assuming uncontrolled motion (i.e., $\mathbf{T}_i^c(t) = \mathbf{0}, \forall t$). Data used in the NLP algorithm for computing the cost matrices are provided in Tables 3 and 4. All the computations were conducted in MATLAB R2023a on a laptop with eight 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 2.3 GHz processors using a 64-bit Windows operating system and 32 GB of RAM. The built-in function *fmincon* with the *interior-point* algorithm was employed to solve Problem 2, and the computation was parallelized using the *parfor* function.

Table 4: Cost Matrices Computation Data

Parameter	Unit	Value
Mission start date	-	01-Jan-2023
M_{dry}	kg	300
M_0	kg	700
$T_{M,0}$	days	0
ΔT_M	days	1650
N_M	-	11
N_T	-	22

6.1 Cost Matrix Inspection

For the twelve-satellite scenario, the computation involved 36432 NLP optimizations and required 1.8 hours.

Figure 5 shows the elements of $\Delta V_{opt,jk}$ and $ToF_{opt,jk}$ matrices for all $j, k \in \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$ in the case of $N_{sat} = 12$. Each matrix element is identified on the abscissa axis. Simulations with the same initial mass and departure time are represented with the same color. The dependence on variables j and k (i.e., dependence on the initial and target orbits) can be observed from the variation along the vertical axis, where zero values associated with $j = k$ cases are also included.

In Fig. 5a, most transfers show a cost ranging from 0.3 km/s to 4 km/s, while the most expensive transfers require an increment in velocity of about 8 km/s. This range of ΔV provides insights into the dispersion of Keplerian elements of satellites as the servicer's initial mass and departure time change.

From Fig. 5b, two main pieces of information can be captured. First, some transfers do not satisfy the maximum time of flight constraint. Second, most transfers converge to a solution requiring exactly the maximum time of flight ToF_{max} . This result is consistent with the considerations made in Sec. 3.2 concerning the well-posedness of the NLP problem.

6.2 Application Case 1: Open Tour Problem

The first application case addresses an optimal open tour problem where the servicer, initially positioned in a specific orbit, must visit all satellites exactly once while minimizing the total fuel consumption. Defining the sets $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, N_{sat}\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, N_{sat} - 1\}$, the combinatorial path problem can be stated as follows

Problem 4. Open Tour Problem

$$\min_{\mathcal{D}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{sat}-1} m_{i,j} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta V_{C,j(j+1)}}{I_{sp} g_0}} \right)$$

subject to

Figure 5: Cost matrices inspection
Table 5: Genetic Algorithm Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
N_{pop}	100
N_{gen}	500
N_{stall}	50
N_{run}	100

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{i,1} &= T_{M_0} \\
 m_{i,1} &= M_0 \\
 t_{i,j+1} &= t_{i,j} + ToF_{C,j(j+1)} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{M} \\
 m_{i,j+1} &= m_{i,j} \cdot e^{-\frac{\Delta V_{C,j(j+1)}}{I_{sp90}}} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{M} \\
 d_1 &= 1 \\
 d_j &\neq d_k \quad \forall j, k \in \mathcal{K}, j \neq k \\
 |\mathcal{D}| &= N_{sat}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $|\mathcal{D}|$ indicates the cardinality of set \mathcal{D} .

The problem described above was solved using the genetic algorithm discussed in Sec.5. Table 5 reports the user-defined parameters for this application case. The optimization was executed $N_{run} = 100$ times in parallel and took 44 s.

Subsequently, the optimal sequence was evaluated by using Eqs. 5 and 6 to validate the results. Table 6 reports the optimal tour, the associated costs in terms of fuel and time of flight, and the absolute percentage errors compared to the non-approximated function evaluations. The low percentage errors observed confirm the accuracy of the proposed methodology. The trajectories of the optimal sequence, represented by the Keplerian elements (a , i , and Ω) for both the servicer and clients, are shown in Fig. 6. The three-phase maneuver structure is highlighted,

and the RAAN precession of the client orbits is visible (see Fig. 6c). Notably, the clients are visited in a monotonically decreasing RAAN pattern. This behavior, referred to as *RAAN walk*, was initially identified in [27] for the time-independent case and is also observed in this time-dependent application.

The servicer mass and mean acceleration magnitude histories are shown in Fig. 7. During the phasing maneuvers, the mass is almost constant because control acceleration is applied only to counteract the drag. The mean acceleration is primarily influenced by the eclipse phases, which reduce the available acceleration and increase the transfer times of the propulsive phases.

6.3 Application Case 2: On-orbit Refueling Problem

The second application case involves a modified version of the combinatorial problem known as the *Knapsack Problem* [28]. In this scenario, the servicer, starting from a specific initial orbit and carrying a limited amount of fuel M_{fuel} , aims at refueling as many clients as possible. The problem is generalized to account for the relative importance of each client, which is quantified by a priority factor $W_i \geq 0$. Additionally, servicing operations require a time T_{ope} during which the servicer provides a fixed amount M_{ope} of fuel to the client. Defining the sets $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, N_{or}\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, N_{or} - 1\}$, the problem can be stated as follows

Problem 5. On-orbit Refueling Problem

Table 6: Optimal Sequence Results and Validation: Case 1

Optimal sequence	ΔM_{tot} (kg)	ToF_{tot} (days)	$\Delta M_{tot,err}$ (%)	$ToF_{tot,err}$ (%)
{1, 2, 8, 6, 4, 3, 5, 11, 9, 7, 10, 12}	115.43	1437.6	3.27	0.01

(a) Semi-major axes

(b) Inclination

(c) Right Ascension of the Ascending Node

Figure 6: Keplerian elements trajectory: case 1

Figure 7: Mass and acceleration magnitude histories: case 1

Table 7: Additional Satellites' Initial Keplerian Elements

ID	a (km)	i (deg)	Ω (deg)
Satellite - 13	7127.60	86.39	150.9
Satellite - 14	7064.04	87.55	56.76
Satellite - 15	6988.20	88.71	124.0
Satellite - 16	7144.54	87.09	74.86
Satellite - 17	7160.00	85.28	107.3
Satellite - 18	7163.30	85.81	117.1
Satellite - 19	7125.67	87.53	175.4
Satellite - 20	7305.55	89.52	174.0

$$\min_{\mathcal{D}} \left(- \sum_{j=1}^{N_{or}} W_{d_j} \right)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} t_{i,1} &= T_{M_0} \\ m_{i,1} &= M_0 \\ t_{i,j+1} &= t_{i,j} + ToF_{C,j(j+1)} + T_{ope} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{M} \\ m_{i,j+1} &= m_{i,j} e^{-\frac{\Delta V_{C,j(j+1)}}{I_{sp90}}} - M_{ope} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{M} \\ m_{i,N_{or}} &\geq M_0 - M_{fuel} \\ d_1 &= 1 \\ d_j &\neq d_k \quad \forall j, k \in \mathcal{K}, j \neq k \\ N_{or} &\leq N_{sat} \\ |\mathcal{D}| &= N_{or} \end{aligned}$$

Eight satellites from IRIDIUM were added to those reported in Table 1. Their initial Keplerian elements are provided in Table 7. The matrices $\Delta V_{opt,jk}$ and $ToF_{opt,jk}$ were computed using the values reported in Tables 2,3, and 4 for all possible transfers. The computation involved 104880 NLP optimizations and took 5.2 hours. Table 8 reports the simulation data for this application case. The genetic algorithm was employed with the parameters specified in Table 5 and adapted to consider the specific equality and inequality constraints of the problem.

Table 8: Simulation Data for On-Orbit Refueling Problem

W	M_{fuel} (kg)	M_{ope} (kg)	T_{ope} (days)
[0, 1, 3, 2, 3, 1, 3, 4, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 3, 4, 1, 2, 3, 2]	400	25	10

The algorithm converged in 36 seconds, revealing various optimal tours with equivalent objective function values. The tour associated with the minimum fuel depletion is detailed in Table 9. The validation results show very small percentage errors, highlighting the method's efficiency and the suitability of the discretization used in generating the cost matrices. Figures 8, and 9 show the Keplerian elements trajectories (a , i and Ω) of both servicer and targets, and the servicer mass and mean acceleration histories, respectively. Servicing phases are also shown.

7. Conclusion

In this work, we combine and expand approaches previously introduced [5], [19] to address space logistics problems involving low-thrust space trajectories. The general problem encompasses mixed integer/continuous and functional variables.

The functional problem is first analyzed and solved by using a three-phase maneuver that considers the effects of secular nodal precession, drag, eclipse, fuel mass depletion, and a two-parameter optimal drift orbit. In order to address a generic path optimization problem, we used the *Time-Varying Matrix Interpolation* method. This approach involves two main steps: first, two matrices quantifying the ΔV and time of flight for each possible transfer are computed by solving the functional problem for discrete sets of initial servicer mass and departure times. Second, bilinear interpolation is applied to these matrices to derive continuous cost functions. The resulting combinatorial problem is then efficiently solved using a genetic algorithm.

We demonstrate the effectiveness of this methodology through two application cases. The first involves an optimal open tour problem, where the servicer must visit all client satellites once, minimizing total fuel consumption. The second case focuses on on-orbit refueling, where the servicer aims at refueling as many satellites as possible, considering priority indices for each client, servicing time, and fuel mass constraints. Results are presented for datasets

(a) Semi-major axes

(b) Inclination

(c) Right Ascension of the Ascending Node

Figure 8: Keplerian elements trajectory: case 2

Figure 9: Mass and acceleration magnitude histories: case 2

Table 9: Optimal Sequence Results and Validation: Case 2

Optimal sequence	ΔM_{tot} (kg)	ToF_{tot} (days)	$\Delta M_{tot,err}$ (%)	$ToF_{tot,err}$ (%)
{1, 19, 5, 8, 4, 3, 9, 7, 16, 15}	291.4	1292.5	0.03	5.16×10^{-5}

consisting of twelve and twenty Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites, respectively. The accuracy of the results is validated by comparing the total mass depletion and time of flight with those obtained by solving the non-approximated functional problem.

The main computational challenge resides in computing the cost matrices. However, the algorithm is well-suited to parallel programming, enabling its application to large datasets. Moreover, once computed, these same cost matrices can be utilized to solve various path optimization problems considering multiple constraints across different mission scenarios when the same spacecraft is employed. Limitations arise solely from the assumptions made in addressing the functional problem.

Appendix

Averaged Dynamics Equations

The averaged dynamics equations utilized in [22] are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di}{dt} &= \frac{2f \sin \beta}{\pi V} \\ \frac{dV}{dt} &= -f \cos \beta \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where f is the control acceleration, β is the thrust yaw angle (i.e., the angle between the thrust vector and the orbit plane), while i and V are the average inclination and orbital velocity magnitude of the satellite, respectively. The assumptions and the complete derivation of Eqs. 12 are detailed in [22].

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